

ly equivalent. These bands are accounted for two non-identical linkages, i.e. C=N-O---H and C=N-O-H, respectively. This observation is consistent with the results of X-ray diffractational analysis of the Cu(DH)₂ complexes in which two different Cu-N distances were observed⁷. The IR bands at around 720–740 cm⁻¹ and 2020–2030 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to the bending and stretching modes, respectively, of the azide group, indicating terminal N-bonding of this group. The stretching vibration, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the free (non-coordinated) DH₂ appearing at 1620–1630 cm⁻¹ consequently shifted in this azidocobaloximes to 1570 cm⁻¹. A very weak intensity band observed at 1720–1750 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the deformation mode of the strong intramolecular hydrogen bridge as it disappeared on deuteration and does suggest a *trans*-configuration for the azido cobaloximes⁸. The characteristic $\nu_{\text{Co-N}}$ (N of DH⁻) appeared at 512 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{\text{Co-N}}$ (of L) appeared around 420 cm⁻¹.

The ¹H NMR spectra of these cobaloximes have been discussed in terms of their *trans* structure¹⁰. The ¹H NMR shifts of the complexes clearly show that on coordination, the signal due to CH₃ group of DH₂ at δ 1.98 undergoes a clear down-field shift and observed at δ 2.36–2.40. In all the complexes, this signal appeared as a sharp singlet indicating the equivalence of four methyl groups and presence of *trans* structure. Free ethylamine ligand showed peaks at δ 0.8, 1.45 and 1.65 for CH₃, CH₂ and NH₂ protons, respectively. In azidocobaloximes where ethyl amine as axial ligand, this peaks appears at δ 0.95, 1.65 and 2.60 ppm. The NH₂ proton chemical shifts of all these complexes observed in the downfield region (2.20–2.70 ppm) compared to free ligands. In all the other complexes the shifts follows the same trend.

The ¹³C NMR chemical shifts followed the same trends of downfield shifts and were also assigned. The oxime CH₃ carbon shows a very sharp signal in free dimethylglyoxime at δ 9.23 which shifted downfield in these complexes to 12.20–12.80 ppm. The presence of only one signal for all the four carbons indicates the equivalence of four CH₃ groups and confirms the *trans*-configuration for these complexes. The imine carbon (C=N) chemical shifts appeared at 151.0–153.0 ppm, which is slightly upfield compared to the value for free DH₂ (154.12 ppm). The ¹³C NMR signals of the alkylamine ligands also underwent downfield shift in the complexes in comparison with free ligands (41.2–45.1).

Experimental

Cobalt(II) acetate, KN₃, dimethylglyoxime and methylamine, ethylamine, *n*-propylamine, *n*-butylamine, hydroxyl-

amine hydrochloride, ethanolamine, cyclohexylamine, cycloheptylamine, benzylamine, 2-chloro benzylamine were used.

[Co(DH)₂(N₃)L], where L = primary amines : The complexes were prepared by bubbling air for 2–6 h through an ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) acetate, KN₃, dimethylglyoxime and the ligands taken in a 1 : 2 : 2 : 2 proportion. The solution was allowed to stand and the resulting crystalline solid was washed with EtOH, Et₂O and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. The reaction presumably proceeds in the following manner :

The aerial oxidation time period was 2 to 6 h. Yields of all the brown complexes were 40–75%.

Cobalt content was determined by reported method¹¹. Micro analysis of complexes were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR 1605 instrument and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian Gemini 200 NMR spectrometer and referenced to TMS.

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